

ESA Climate Change Initiative CCI+

Annex to Product User Guide

SNOW
cci

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Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim

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ESA STUDY CONTRACT REPORT			
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<p>Abstract:</p> <p>The European Space Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative aims to generate high quality Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) derived from long-term satellite data records to meet the needs of climate research and monitoring activities. The main goal of the <i>snow_cci</i> project is to generate homogeneous, well-calibrated, long-term time series of the key snow cover variables snow area extent and snow mass for climate applications. <i>snow_cci</i> Option 2 <i>Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim</i> has advanced the original CryoClim binary product to an FSC product.</p> <p>This document is a user guide for the snow product produced in Option 2 of the <i>snow_cci</i> project. The product, <i>snow_cci</i> CryoClim fractional snow cover (FSC), is based on multi-sensor/multi-temporal analysis of data from the sensors AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS. The retrieved entity represents snow on the ground (SCFG). An estimate of the uncertainty at the per-pixel level is available as a separate data layer in the product (RMSE SCFG). The document provides a comprehensive description of the thematic content of the product and its coding. It also includes a description of known limitations and strengths of the product.</p>			
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA Contract. Responsibility for the contents resides in the author or organisation that prepared it.</p>			
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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose and Scope

The European Space Agency (ESA) Climate Change Initiative aims to generate high-quality Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) derived from long-term satellite data records to meet the needs of climate research and monitoring activities, including the detection of variability and trends, climate modelling, and aspects of hydrology and meteorology. The Climate Research Data Package (CRDP) for the ESA CCI+ snow Option-2 project *Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim* closely follows the CRDP of the *snow_cci* baseline project. The product, *snow_cci* CryoClim fractional snow cover (FSC), is based on multi-sensor/multi-temporal analysis of data from the sensors AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS. The retrieved entity represents snow on the ground (SCFG). An estimate of the uncertainty at the per-pixel level is available as a separate data layer in the product (RMSE SCFG).

1.2. Document Structure

Following this introduction section, the product generated within the Option 2 - *Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim*, is presented in Section 2. The file format and how to access the products is covered in Section 3. Finally follows references in Section 4.

1.3. Applicable and Reference Documents

- [AD-1] Phase 1 of the ESA Climate Change Initiative CCI+ New ECVS (Snow). ESRIN Contract No: 4000124098/18/I-NB.
- [AD-2] Climate Change Initiative Extension (CCI+) Phase 1 – New Essential Climate Variables (Annex E: Snow ECV (*snow_cci*), ESA-CCI-PRGM-EOPS-SW-17-0032.
- [AD-3] Technical Proposal (Part 3) in response to ESA Climate Change Initiative Phase 1 ESA ITT AO/1-9041/17/I-NB, ENVEO Innsbruck, Austria.
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- [RD-8] Solberg, R., Killie, M. A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Product Specification Document, v1.0
- [RD-9] Solberg, R., Killie, M. A., Rudjord, Ø., Eastwood, S., Sørensen, A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Data Access Requirements Document, version 1.1
- [RD-10] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Salberg, A.-B., Killie, M. A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Algorithm Development Plan, version 1.0
- [RD-11] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Salberg, A.-B., Killie, M. A. (2021). ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Product Validation Plan, version 1.0
- [RD-12] Solberg, R., Rudjord, Ø., Killie, M. A., Sørensen, A. M., Eastwood, S. (2021) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document, version 2.0.
- [RD-13] Salberg, A.-B., Solberg, R. (2021) ESA CCI+ Snow ECV, Option 2 - Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim: Annex to End-to-End ECV Uncertainty Budget, version 2.0.
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1.4. Acronyms

AATSR	Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer
ATSR-2	Along-Track Scanning Radiometer
AMSR	Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer
AVHRR	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DMSP	Defence Meteorological Satellite Program
CP	Contractual Phase
DARD	Data Access Requirement Document
ECV	Essential Climate Variable
ESA	European Space Agency
FSC	Fractional Snow Cover
GAC	Global Area Coverage
GCMD	Global Change Master Directory
MetOp	European Meteorological Operational Satellite
MODIS	Moderate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NDSI	Normalized Difference Snow Index
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
PMR	Passive Microwave Radiometer
PVP	Product Validation Plan
QA4EO	Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SCF	Snow Cover Fraction
SCFG	Snow Cover Fraction, snow on the Ground
SCFV	Snow Cover Fraction, Viewable snow
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer
SMMR	Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer
SSM/I	Special Sensor Microwave/Imager
SSMIS	Special Sensor Microwave Imager / Sounder
SWE	Snow Water Equivalent
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
WGS	World Geodetic System

2. PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

2.1. Overall Description

The overall aim of the *snow_cci* CryoClim fractional snow cover (FSC) climate data record is to provide one of the longest snow cover extent time series available with global coverage and without hindrance from clouds and polar night. This has been achieved by utilising the best features of optical and passive microwave radiometer (PMR) observations of snow using a sensor-fusion algorithm generating a consistent time series of global FSC products (Solberg et al. 2014, 2015; Rudjord et al. 2015). The *snow_cci* Option-2 project *Fractional Snow Cover in CryoClim* has advanced the original CryoClim binary product to an FSC product. The thematic variable represents snow on the ground (SCFG).

AVHRR sensors aboard the satellites NOAA-7, -9, -11, -14, -16, -18, -19, MetOp-A and MetOp-B have been used as the optical data source, and SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS sensors aboard the satellites Nimbus 7, DMSP F8, DMSP F11, and from DMSP F13 to DMSP F18, respectively, have been used as PMR data source. To achieve temporally stable data, we use fundamental climate data records (FCDRs) as input provided by EUMETSAT Climate Monitoring Satellite Application Facility (CM SAF). These data cover the period 01.01.1982-31.12.2020 for optical (Karlsson et al. 2020) and 01.01.1982-31.12.2015 for PMR (Fenning et al. 2017). To make an interim extension of the time series until 31.12.2023, we have used interim data (near real-time data) with AVHRR GAC data for optical used by EUMETSAT to generate CLARA A3 products (Karlsson et al. 2023) and for PMR operational SSMIS data from NOAA (NOAA 2023).

The characteristics of the *snow_cci* CryoClim FSC product is shown in Table 2.1

Table 2.1: CryoClim FSC product prototype characteristics.

Subject	CryoClim Fractional Snow Cover CRDP prototype version
Variable	Fractional snow cover [%]
Accuracy target	10-20% unbiased RMSE
Retrieval algorithm	Solberg et al. 2014, 2015; Rudjord et al. 2015; adapted from a binary variable to FSC
Uncertainty algorithm	Salberg et al. 2022 [RD-13]
Cloud screening algorithm	N/A
Satellite(s)	NOAA-7, -9, -11, -14, -16, -18, -19, MetOp-A, MetOp-B; Nimbus-7, DMSP F8, - F11, - F13 -- F18
Sensor(s)	AVHRR, SMMR, SSM/I and SSMIS
Input product(s)	Level-1B FCDRs from EUMETSAT CM SAF
Geographical domain(s)	Global
Start date time series	01.01.1982
End date time series	31.12.2023
Grid size	0.05°
Projection/datum	Geographical (lat/lon)/WGS 84

<i>Subject</i>	<i>CryoClim Fractional Snow Cover CRDP prototype version</i>
Temporal resolution	Daily
Temporal aggregation	None
Number of layers	2
Metadata	Global attributes in NetCDF4 file, CF-v1.9, conformal with CCI data standards v2.3, 26/07/2021
Auxiliary data	The source of the land, waterbody and land ice masks is GlobCover version 2.2 (Bicheron et al. 2008). Historical model temperature data from ERA-Interim global atmospheric reanalysis (Dee et al. 2011) is used to cover the optical snow cover algorithm's need for model surface temperature data
Data representation	Unsigned byte (8 bits)
File format	NetCDF4, CF-v1.9
Product access	https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/f4654030223445b0bac63a23aaa60620/

2.2. Data Representation

The coding of the product and the associated uncertainty estimation is described in Table 2.2 and Table 2.3, respectively.

Table 2.2: Coding applied for the CryoClim FSC product.

<i>Code(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>
0-100	FSC [%]; 0 = snow free; 100 = fully snow covered
210	Water
215	Glaciers, icecaps, ice sheets
255	Not valid data
All other values	Not used

Table 2.3: Coding applied for the associated CryoClim FSC uncertainty product.

<i>Code(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>
0-100	Estimate of RMSE [% FSC]
210	Water
215	Glaciers, ice caps, ice sheets
254	ERROR: No satellite acquisition
255	Not Valid Pixel
All other values	Not used

Figure 2.1: CryoClim FSC product example for 1 April 2014.

Figure 2.2: CryoClim FSC uncertainty product example for 1 April 2014.

2.3. Known Strengths and Limitations

Strengths: The product provides the fraction of snow cover on the ground per grid cell on global land areas, except for glaciers. The data record provides one of the longest snow cover time series available with global coverage and without hindrance from clouds and polar night on a daily temporal resolution. The spatial resolution of the product, 0.05° grid size, is high compared to other available satellite-based global snow products providing full spatial coverage on a daily basis year around (i.e. also for areas covered by clouds and polar night), which are all based on PMR data only of typically 10-25 km resolution. The product provides snow on the ground (SCFG), compensating potential obstructed view

from vegetation canopy. The product quality is high, as validation results gave an overall accuracy with an RMSE in the order of 16% and a bias lower than 2.4%. The product comes with uncertainty estimates on the grid-cell level.

Limitations: The quality of the input data was not optimal all through the first two decades of the time series due to sensor limitations, sensor-band failures and orbital drift of satellites. Bias associated with Nimbus 7 SMMR and DMSP F-8 SSM/I has been observed, in particular in the summer period with almost only wet and patchy snow present. SMMR did not have the 85 GHz channel, and the channel failed on DMSP F-8 after a period. The bias seems to be most pronounced in the summer season. We therefore recommended caution for regions of patchy/wet snow in the summer period for the years 1982-1991. There are periods of unfavourable illumination conditions with the early NOAA satellites due to orbital drift and less favourable passage timing over time. The problem is most prominent when data from only one satellite is available (in particular NOAA-12). When more satellites became available and satellites were launched into an orbit with equatorial passage time closer to noon in the late 1990s, the problem became less pronounced. In the last 25 years or so there has been more redundancy (more sensors in orbit) and therefore no periods of reduced quality.

3. COMMON FILE FORMAT AND ACCESS DESCRIPTION

The file format and access advice follow the *snow_cci* baseline project [RD-6], including filename convention, global and variable attributes, and metadata. See documents at <https://snow-cci.enveo.at/>

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- NOAA, 2023. Special Sensor Microwave Imager/Sounder (SSMIS) Sensor Data Record (SDR) in netCDF. (SSMIS SDR data from NOAA CLASS (accessed through EUMETCast), ERA5T) <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.ncdc:C00797;view=html>